

ORGANIZATION OF REGIONAL TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE OCCUPIED TERRITORIES OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN - KARABAKH REGIONAL TRANSPORT PLANNING

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Abstract

The Patriotic War, which began on September 27, 2020, in response to another military provocation committed by the Armed Forces of the Republic of Armenia against our country, ended 44 days later with a historic victory of the Azerbaijani nation and the territories which were under occupation for 30 years were liberated. As a result of ensuring the territorial integrity of our country, necessary measures are being taken to restore the liberated territories, build new economic and social infrastructure, support economic activity and ensure well-deserved living conditions.

Considering the need for a comprehensive and systematic approach to the restoration of transport infrastructure and organization of services in the liberated territories, the article lists proposals for the organization of regional transport infrastructure in the liberated territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the “Action Program” for Karabakh regional transport planning.

The article identifies issues to be addressed and the measures to be taken in the process of building transport infrastructure and services in Karabakh, including requirements and approaches, expedient planning of available resources and activities related to the organization of qualitative transport services in accordance with standards, norms and rules established by existing regulations in the field of transport.

The main purpose of the article is identification of necessary measures in order to establish mobile and stable transport networks in accordance with modern requirements for the comprehensive integration of the liberated territories into a single transport quarter (system), to ensure quality and uninterrupted transport system, organization of transport and logistics services and ensuring continuity and sustainability of these services.

Keywords: Regional transport planning, “One pipeline, one road”, Caspian bridge, Turkish corridor, East Zangazur, transport-logistics services, logistics performance index, highways, transport scheme, logistics center.

1. Introduction

Immediately after the great victory, it was determined that the transport networks of the region were insufficient and that the living quarters, as well as the transport infrastructure, were completely useless. For this reason, measures are being taken to improve and reconstruct residential areas, develop the main transport infrastructure, roads, railways, and airport networks. These investments are essential to ensure the return to the liberated areas, restoration and improvement work, as well as the sustainable growth of safe accommodation, productive activities and prosperity.

This study will identify the needs of regional transport networks, considering investments in the construction, planned transport infrastructure and settlements in the region, and assess the need for new transport corridor proposals.

2. Scope

The study aims to: provide safe, comfortable, and fast access to the region, increase the region's attractiveness, provide the highest level of access to settlements, military and logistics, and identify new investments suitable for additional needs.

The initial goals and objectives of this study are as follows:

Objective 1 – Interregional adaptation: to create a unified transport system that will meet the travel (mobility) needs of users and provide efficient, sustainable, effective freight and passenger transportation systems between all regions of the country.

- **Goal 1.1:** Link all liberated areas with road, rail and air transport infrastructure connecting major regional centers.

- **Goal 1.2:** Create complementary road, rail and air transport opportunities and capabilities that will enable citizens to travel within the country in a sustainable and cost-effective manner by 2040.

- **Goal 1.3:** Create complementary road, rail and air transport capacity and capabilities that will ensure sustainable and cost-effective freight transport within the country by 2040.

Objective 2 – Becoming a regional center in the field of transport and logistics services: to make Azerbaijan a regional center in the field of transport and logistics services in accordance with its geographical advantages, by making the investment in logistics services attractive and creating a transport and logistics sector that will create added value as well as new job opportunities.

- **Goal 2.1:** to support transport and logistics services to be comparable to the top 15 countries in the Logistics Performance Index.

- **Goal 2.2:** to establish links between the countries of the Far East and the countries of the Middle East and Europe, as well as between the Turkic states.

- **Goal 2.3:** to create a transport and logistics sector that provides a service that competes with neighboring countries in terms of price and quality.

Objective 3 – Safety: to create a transport system that will ensure a high level of safety for users and significantly reduce the number of deaths and serious injuries on the roads.

- **Goal 3.1:** to further reduce the number of fatal road accidents in 2030 compared to 2020 and to achieve the goals set by the government by 2031.

Objective 4 - National Security: to build a transport network in the region that meets defense needs.

- **Goal 4.1:** Establish a transport network on routes that can be used by security units with identification of security corridors that can meet defense needs.

The scope of regional transport planning in Karabakh, which is the subject of this study, covers the liberated regions of Agdam, Jabrayil, Fizuli, Kalbajar, Lachin, Gubadli, Shusha, Tartar, Khankendi, Khojaly, Khojavend, and Zangilan.

3. Available information and statistics

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan: No. 1386 dated July 7, 2021 "On the new division of economic regions in the Republic of Azerbaijan", the research area is divided into 2 economic zones:

- *Karabakh economic region (Khankendi city, Agjabadi, Aghdam, Barda, Fuzuli, Khojaly, Khojavend, Shusha and Tartar regions),*

- *East Zangazur economic region (Jabrayil, Kalbajar, Gubadli, Lachin and Zangilan regions).*

There are 585 km of highways in the region, only 1,563 km of national roads, 1,522 km of local roads and a total of 8,560 km of other roads. The following table shows the pre-occupation national highways in Karabakh and East Zangazur economic regions.

Table 5.

Available road indices		
Road number and index	Road name / encription	Length of the road (km)
M-6	Hajigabul-Bahramtepe-Minjivan-State border with the Republic of Armenia	286
R-19	Ganja-Kalbajar-Lachin	200
R-27	Tartar-Hindarx	41
R-28	Yevlakh-Khojaly-Lachin	151
	Access road to Khankendi	1
	Access road to Shusha	2
	Entrance to the city of Kalbajar	4
R-30	Khankendi-Khojavend	42
R-31	Shusha-Fuzuli	53
R-33	Aghdam-Hindarkh-Agjabadi	48
R-34	Aghdam-Aghdara	26
R-35	Aghdam-Fuzuli-Horadiz	90
	Entrance road to Khojavend city	4
R-36	Lachin-Hakari	83
R-37	Lachin-Zabukh State border with the Republic of Armenia	23
R-38	Gubadli-Khanate	16
R-39	Hakari-Zangilan	23
R-40	Fuzuli-Jabrayil-Mahmudlu	46
	Other	465
	Total	1563

There is a need to upgrade almost all road networks in the areas. No investment has been made in the research network for 30 years, and most roads have been destroyed.

The existing Horadiz-Jabrayil-Zangilan-Agband road, Gubadli-Lachin, Shukurbayli-Jabrayil-Hadrut

road, Ahmadbeyli-Fuzuli-Shusha, Fuzuli-Hadrut, Barda-Agdam roads are in a very bad condition in terms of transport, operational indicators and geometric parameters and in many places there are ruins of roads which looks like a dirt road.

Most of the Togana-Kalbajar and Kalbajar-Lachin highways currently serve as dirt roads and are very slow. These roads, which are classified as roads of national importance in the network of highways, have in fact become uncatagorized, non-asphalt roads.

The occupied parts of the Agjabadi-Aghdam road (Hajimammadli-Aghdam) are also one of the roads in need of restoration.

The largest number of vehicles, about 25,000, are registered in the Aghdam region. The next region with the largest number of vehicles is Fizuli with 15,000 vehicles. There are less than 5,000 vehicles in Khojavend, Khojaly, Shusha, Zangilan and Gubadli districts.

The total number of vehicles registered in the study area is 86,290, which is 6% of the total (1,418,404) vehicles registered in the Republic of Azerbaijan. It is possible to say that the indicators in the field of research are low compared to the number of cars per capita in the country.

The length of the existing railway line in and around the study area is 1,189 km and has a total of 32 stations. The most important stations are Agdam, Khojaly, Khankendi, Agjabadi, Zangilan, Yevlakh and Ganja. While the territories were under occupation, the railways between Horadiz-Agband and Barda-Agdam were completely destroyed and rendered as unfit for usage.

According to the statistics of 2020, the rate of railway use in the transport sector of the country was implemented in the following ratios.

- Cargo transportation 7.8%,
- Intercity passenger traffic is about 1.0%,
- Suburban passenger traffic 0.76%.

Compared to road, rail transport was less frequent (especially passenger transport).

4. Background information, statistics, project proposals and planning

Four main goals should play a role in the formation of the transport structure of the Karabakh region:

- **Objective 1.** To ensure the integration of the region into the international transport system with other regions of the country and through transport corridors.
- **Objective 2.** Ensuring access to the transport infrastructure of the settlements forming the region, including service and production areas.

- **Objective 3.** Ensuring accessibility and increasing transport efficiency through integration between modes of transport.

- **Objective 4.** Stimulation of environmentally friendly modes of transport for the region, organization of modern public transport services, creation of a network of bicycle infrastructure, and introduction of new modes of transport.

The Dashkasan-Kalbajar corridor in the north-west, Barda-Agdam in the north-east, Agjabedi-Agdam in the east, Beylagan-Ahmadbeyli in the southeast and Nakhchivan-Agband corridors in the south-west should be planned as the main entrances to the region and close ties with other regions should be organized. The region should be connected with the neighboring countries of the region, as well as through the Arazbayli-Agband corridor and the Fizuli, Zangilan, Gorchu international airports.

The 155-kilometer section of the Arazboyu-Nakhchivan-Turkey-Europe transport corridor (Zangazur corridor) starting from the Baku International Sea Trade Port in Alat settlement, located between Ahmadbeyli and Agband, plays an important role in the development of planning strategies in the Karabakh region. Thus, this part is proposed as a development corridor, providing industrial/logistics type activities, starting from the city of the regional center, Agdam.

In the future, planning solutions may be considered for the extension of the Ahmadbeyli-Horadiz-Minjivan-Agband highway to Alat settlement, the creation of an independent route for the international corridor, and the construction of a new road bridge over the Araz River between Azerbaijan and Iran (already offered).

In addition, to increase the capacity of international transport corridors passing through our country and create new international transport corridors, the Historical Silk Road (Turkish Corridor) - "TRACECA" on the Europe-Caucasus-Asia transport corridor", which reduce distances, facilitate transit transport links between countries, joint road and railway bridge plan (Caspian Bridge) directly connecting Azerbaijan (Alat) and Turkmenistan (Turkmenbashi) across the Caspian Sea in order to create a strong integration between Europe and Asia, is very important in terms of achieving goals.

The route map for the proposed extension of the Ahmadbeyli-Horadiz-Minjivan-Agband highway to Alat settlement and for the proposed new Caspian Bridge, is shown below.

Figure 4. Khazar bridge

The Araz Valley, economic zone in Soltanli, the Logistics Center in Minjivan, and the Solid Waste Management Center between Soltanli and Gumlaq are the main investment projects designed and proposed along this corridor. Fuzuli International Airport, which is being built on this development corridor, and Zangilan International Airport, which is being designed, are also transport infrastructures that have a strong impact on the development of the corridor.

The Ahmadbeyli-Fuzuli-Shusha corridor, designed and currently under construction, consists of 2 highways and 1 railway line. The design of Shusha-Khankendi-Khojaly-Agdam section of the railway between Ahmadbeyli-Fuzuli-Shusha and Barda-Agdam railways, has been proposed which provides a ring structure, make transport more fluent and increase accessibility. One of the proposals is to extend the railway from Arazboy to Agjabadi to the city of Agdam. Thus, Aghdam will be a strong regional center where railways and highways from Barda, Shusha and Agjabadi intersect.

The projected Shukurbayli-Jabrayil-Hadrut-Fuzuli highways connect the important settlements with each other and with other main modes of transport (Fuzuli International Airport, Ahmadbeyli-Fuzuli-Shusha railway and highways, Ahmadbeyli-Horadiz-Agband railway and highways) are considered major investments for the purpose of building and strengthening.

At the same time, it was proposed to strengthen the existing local roads between Hadrut-Horadiz, Jabrayil-Soltanli, Jabrayil-Turshsu and Jabrayil-Balasoltanli-Gubadli and convert these into national roads.

The main roads proposed for construction in the region for infrastructure measures are:

1. "Ahmadbeyli - Fuzuli - Shusha" ("Victory Road", performed),

2. "Ahmadbeyli - Fuzuli - Shusha" highway,
3. "Talysh - Tapgaragoyunlu - Gashalti sanatorium" highway,
4. "Barda - Aghdam" highway,
5. "Horadiz - Jabrayil - Zangilan - Agband" highway,
6. "Togana - Kalbajar - Istisu" highway,
7. "Khudaferin - Gubadli - Lachin", a new highway without entering the city of Lachin,
8. "Shukurbayli - Jabrayil - Hadrut" highway,
9. "Fuzuli - Hadrut" highway,
10. "Kalbajar - Lachin" highway,
11. "Aghdam-Fuzuli" highway,
12. "Gubadli - Eyvazli" highway,
13. "Gubadli-Mahmudlu-Yazduzu-state border with the Republic of Armenia" highway,
14. "Hadrut - Tug - Azykh" highway,
15. "Istisu-Minkend-Lachin" highway,
16. Construction of road infrastructure in Pirjahan-Goshasu, Kalbajar and Lachin districts,
17. "Jabrayil - Balasoltanli (Gubadli)" highway,
18. "Jabrayil - Turshsu", "Balasoltanli (Gubadli) - Gubadli" highway,
19. "Fuzuli-Khankendi" highway,
20. "Shukurbayli - Soltanli (new route)" highway,
21. "Soltanli - Jabrayil" highway,
22. "Horadiz - Hadrut" highway,
23. "Lachin (Safiyan) - Hadrut" highway,
24. "Aghdam-Vangli-Takhtabashi-Bashlibel-Istisu" highway,
25. "Kalbajar-Gadabay" (and Dashkasan) highway,
26. "Zangilan-Alibeyli" highway,
27. Gorchu-Minkend highway,
28. Aghdam outer ring road.

Figure 5. Aghdam city circular highway project

Figure 6. Project progress by 09.09.2021

At the same time, the construction and maintenance of the Beylagan-Khojavend-Fuzuli highway (connecting the newly designed Fuzuli-Agdam highway and the Beylagan-Allahyarli-Alkhanli-Kerimbeyli highway) should be implemented within the framework of projects.

In addition, the repair and reconstruction of highways, as well as the construction of artificial facilities should be considered, which will provide transport links between the villages and settlements to be built in the liberated areas, as well as between the regional centers. It is proposed to connect the centers of 315 identified settlement groups in the region to the nearest republican roads through local roads.

1. "Ahmadbeyli - Fuzuli - Shusha" highway.

- Technical indicators: 81.6 km, "I" technical grade, four lanes.

- Work done: Construction of land in the 0-18, 26-45, 51-53, 58-65, 71-73, 75-81 km sections, bridges are being built at 1, 27, 34, 37, 50, 62, 79 km, tunnels at 80 km and underpasses at 60 km.

2. "Toganali - Kalbajar - Istisu" highway.

- Technical indicators: road - 80.7 km, technical grade "I-II", 2-3 lanes, tunnel - 11.6 km.

- Carried works: excavation of a field in the 12-13 km section of the road, construction of water pipes in the 12.8 and 13.3 km sections and relocation of existing canals. A total of 750 m of upper semi-drilling was carried out at the entrance and exit of the Murovdag tunnel. Due to the winter conditions, maintenance of the roads, snow plowing and distribution of salt-sand mixture will be provided throughout the project.

3. "Kalbajar - Lachin" highway.

- Technical indicators: road - 72.3 km, "I-II" technical level, 2-3 lanes, tunnel - 9.8 km;

- Work done: the construction of the roadbed is 40% completed, mobilization work continues.

4. Construction of road infrastructure in Kalbajar and Lachin districts.

- Technical indicators: 30 km, technical grade "IV", two lanes.

- Work done: construction of roadbed and road wear is underway, construction of pipes is 95% completed, road signs are installed 85%.

5. "Horadiz - Jabrayil - Zangilan - Agband" highway.

- Technical indicators: 123.8 km, "I" technical grade, 4-6 lanes.

- Work done: Construction of a soil field is underway at 0-23 and 42-76 km. Earthworks were carried out by 25%, construction of pipes and crossings by 29%, construction of bridges by 25%.

6. "Khudafarin - Gubadli - Lachin" highway.

- Technical indicators: 70.4 km, "I" technical grade, four lanes.

- Work done: 0-37 km in the direction of Gubadli - Lachin, a field is built at 0-1 and 5-14 km in the direction of Khanlig, bridges are being built at 1, 11, 23, 33 and 39 km. Earthworks were carried out by 37%, road wear by 4%, construction of pipes and crossings by 37%, construction of bridges by 29%.

7. "Gubadli - Eyvazli" highway.

- Technical indicators: 26 km, "IV" technical grade, two lanes.

- Work done: Construction work is underway on the road to Eyvazli village in Gubadli region, destroying rocky soils. Work has been completed to expand the landfill to 8 km of the general road and bring it to the normative width.

8. Shukurbayli-Jabrayil-Hadrut highway.

- Technical indicators: 43 km, "I" technical grade, four lanes.

- Work done: Earthworks 53%, road wear 10%, construction of pipes and crossings 55%, construction of bridges 51%.

9. "Fuzuli - Hadrut" highway.

- Technical indicators: 13 km, "I" technical grade, four lanes.

- Work done: Construction of the roadbed is underway. Earthworks and construction of the roadbed in the first 8 km have been completed by 50%.

10. "Barda - Aghdam" highway.

- Technical indicators: 45 km, "I" technical grade, four lanes.

- Work done: earthworks by 45.9%, road wear by 9.8%, construction of pipes and crossings by 33.5%, construction of bridges by 84.9%.

11. "Talysh - Tapgaragoyunlu - Gashalti - Naftalan" highway.

- Technical indicators: 22 km, "II-IV" technical level, two lanes.

- Work done: In the first 1.8 km part of the road, the bottom layer of asphalt-concrete pavement was built, in 1.8-6 km and 12-22 km sections, pipes are installed, and the foundation is built.

It is proposed to design the 82 + 380 - 102 + 700 km section of the highway in a northerly direction, north of the currently designed route, bypassing the Minjivan settlement, in order to outflank the main road from the settlements and establish the route with a shorter distance. It should be noted that in accordance with the requirements of road design standards, highways should be designed outside settlements. There are several factors determining the effectiveness of the proposal which are stated below:

- the road will be shortened by about 8.9 km in total (due to the shortening of the route, the design of the tunnel on the new route can be provided to some extent).
- The intersection of the road with the existing road of national importance at the entrance of Jahangirbeyli village will be eliminated and more optimal slope of the road will be provided.
- Intersection of the road with the existing water channel at 3 locations will be eliminated.
- Security of Zangilan airport runway will be ensured.
- the road can be re-routed outside Minjivan settlement.
- The residential areas of Minjivan settlement can be used effectively.
- Spatial planning framework can be optimally formed.

It is planned to build new railway lines in 4 directions with a total length of 328.38 km in the liberated territories ("Barda-Aghdam", "Horadiz-Aghdam", "Fuzuli-Shusha" and "Dalimammadli-Kalbajar" railway lines).

Couple of these, the Fuzuli-Shusha and Dalimammadli-Kalbajar railway lines, did not exist before the occupation and are being redesigned.

1. "Barda-Aghdam" railway line:

- length 47.1 km.
- number of stations - 4 (Barda, Kocharli, Tazakend, Aghdam).

The repair work is being carried out in two stages.

Phase I, in the direction of "Barda-Kocharli-Tazakend" (20.78 km). At present, the total physical completion of the first stage is 39%.

Phase II, on "Tazakend-Aghdam" (26.32 km). In order to continue the construction work at this stage, the mine clearance process has not been completed, whereas research work has been completed on the identified route, and in general, 90% of the design work of the railway line and artificial facilities have been completed.

2. "Horadiz-Aghdam" railway line:

- length 110.4 km;
- number of stations - 8 (Horadiz, Marjanli, Mahmudlu, Soltanli, Gumlag, Minjivan, Bartaz, Aghdam).

The design and construction of the railway is planned in 3 stages.

1st stage: it is planned to build a 23 km railway line between the Horadiz-Marjanli-Mahmudlu locations with the existing route, and a new railway line from Mahmudlu to the 30th km. At this stage, the physical topographic plan of the area has been completed.

At present, a total of 53% of the earthworks on the first stage have been completed, the construction and installation of artificial facilities has been completed. Construction of 9 water pipes and 10 bridges is underway.

2nd stage: it is planned to build a new route from the 30th km through Soltanli and Gumlag stations to Minjivan station, and in the third stage at 85-110.4 km through Minjivan, Bartaz and Aghdam stations.

3. "Fuzuli-Shusha" railway line:

- length 82.8 km.
- number of stations - 2.

At present, research and design work of the route has been completed.

4. "Dalimammadli-Kalbajar" railway line:

- length 88.08 km.
- number of stations - 2.

At present, the research and design work of the route is being completed.

In addition, it is proposed to design the Zangilan-Lachin (Gorchu) and Aghdam-Aghjabadi railway lines with a total length of about 120 km.

The projected Dashkasan-Kalbajar railway and Togana-Kalbajar-Istisu-Minkend-Lachin highway will play an important role in the development of Kalbajar region. Another important proposal is the railway line from Agali Agilli village in Arazboy, planned for 2040, to Gorchu International Airport, which is being built after Lachin. The railway stations proposed in the existing important settlements along this line (Agali, Khanlig, Gulebird, Lachin, Pirjahan, Gorchu) will play a key role in the development of the surrounding areas, especially in Lachin, Gubadli, Zangilan districts. The proposed railway line will further strengthen ties with the remaining settlements within the coverage area of Zangilan and Gorchu airports. At the same time, the industrial and commercial activities of these settlements will be supported.

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